

CONSEQUENCES OF CHILDHOOD TRAUMA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922245>

Raximova Roxat Boysoatovna

*Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy, Psychology and Languages
of the Tashkent Medical Academy*

Sandiboyev Otajon Hamroqul o'g'li

1st year student of Tashkent Medical Academy

Annotation.

Trauma is any event that does not correspond with everyday situations and can give rise to feelings of severe stress and unhappiness. Such feelings can disrupt an individual's emotional response system and lead to internal regulation difficulties at a later stage. In this article, we will discuss about the later consequences of childhood trauma and its effects to people's behavior.

Key words.

stress, childhood trauma, low self-esteem, sleep disturbance, depression, anxiety;

Аннотация.

Травма - это любое событие, которое не соответствует повседневным ситуациям и может вызвать чувство сильного стресса и несчастья. Такие чувства могут нарушить систему эмоциональных реакций индивида и привести к трудностям внутренней регуляции на более позднем этапе. В этой статье мы поговорим о более поздних последствиях детской травмы и ее влиянии на поведение людей.

Ключевые слова.

стресс, детская травма, низкая самооценка, нарушение сна, депрессия, тревога

Trauma is any event that does not correspond with everyday situations and can give rise to feelings of severe stress and unhappiness. Emotional struggles as a result of interpersonal trauma could steer emotional vulnerability as feelings of violation and betrayal reside within the sufferer . Such feelings can disrupt an individual's emotional response system and lead to internal regulation difficulties at a later stage .

If trauma has been inflicted on a child by their parent(s), their core belief system recognizes that a secure attachment style has not been formed and is deficient in protection, prompting emotional hesitation. A sense of safety and

support is paramount in the early years to encourage a child to explore their environment confidently and independently, despite any possibility of failure .

In the case where a child becomes familiar with traumatic events, the onset of behavioral issues increases because the victim's neurological structure changes in accordance with the adversities experienced or witnessed. Therefore, resulting in the risk of psychopathology development . This research examines trauma in terms of physical, sexual and emotional abuse and uses this to understand future consequences and management strategies following personal hardship.

This study researches the link between three consequences of childhood trauma that have appeared in previous literature:

1. Depression and anxiety.
2. Sleep disturbance.
3. Low self-esteem.

Childhood trauma has been linked to the development of anxiety and depression in later life and a history of abuse may be more identifiable by adulthood as emotional and behavioral patterns have evolved by this period. As of this, various disorders are likely to arise among childhood abuse victims. More specifically, the connection between depression, anxiety and childhood trauma could be related to the individual's neurological response system. Repeated childhood exposure to severe stressors causes excessive transmission of stress hormones in the body, as a way of responding to the event(s) that are happening around them. Regular exposure to toxic conditions in childhood can distort the biological makeup of the body's Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis. This neurological system sends signals to the brain to alert the body of dangerous circumstances. When the HPA axis is over activated the secretion of stress hormones creates a surplus and the body remains alert in preparation to react to perceived harmful situations through the fight-flight-freeze system. If a state of readiness through this system occurs frequently, it permits over activation throughout childhood and later promotes the risk of depressive and anxiety disorders due to heightened cortisol levels following traumatic episodes .

Sleep disturbance. Overcoming trauma can take its toll on a survivor's mindset and consequentially, rumination over distressing experiences is likely. Sleep issues can lead to poor physical and mental health and exacerbate post-trauma symptoms . Sleep disturbance is arguably a troubling factor for childhood trauma victims as this routine is associated with comfort and safety and once it has been interfered with during childhood, these associated feelings have been removed from the

child's night-time regime. Children who have experienced physical and sexual abuse in the bedroom may struggle to fall asleep and maintain a full night of sleep because they have been personally violated in a typically secure setting . Mirroring this, research indicates that children who have experienced trauma, display signs of sleep disturbance almost instantly and report having nightmares as their most dominant post-trauma symptom .

This being the case, nightmares and sleep disturbance following trauma can represent subconscious feelings of conflict held by the individual. Therefore, responding to and accepting the incident(s) may help minimize the influence it has on one's life. Particularly, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) could guide the sufferer in overcoming negative emotions towards past adversities. Some CBT approaches can help an individual to re-imagine their nightmare but create their desired ending. This allows the individual to feel empowered and in control which may diminish previous emotions and reduce the number of nightmares they are having about their past .

Low self-esteem

If a child's primary caregiver is the purveyor of their trauma, the child could battle with self-esteem problems by adulthood as a result of inadequate relationship and attachment formation . Precisely, abuse can produce feelings of fear and vulnerability within the victims and can drive self-esteem issues following instability in current or previous relationships . For children, abusive trauma destructs self-worth and self-identity because unhealthy relationships in the early years depict uncertainty and poor self-belief . This implies that traumatic experiences from interpersonal relationships contribute to a child's general self-knowledge. From this, they may adopt relationship patterns derived from childhood if the appropriate measures are not utilized to surpass the negative effect of their adversities.

Trauma of any kind has a negative effect on the process of socialization of children. It is difficult for a child to make friends, communicate with new people, adapt to unfamiliar conditions. The psyche of a traumatized baby is prone to the formation of obsessions, fears and social phobias. In adults, the consequences of psychological trauma in childhood are manifested in a high risk of developing depression, in a constant sense of guilt, in irritability and aggression. A long stay in this state negatively affects the well-being and health of a person, he cannot live a full life, experiences difficulties in his personal life and in communication. Psychologists claim that many adult survivors of a traumatic event develop

obsessive-compulsive disorder, which is characterized by the occurrence of illogical obsessive thoughts and the performance of strange protective actions.

Often adults turn to a psychologist for help, complaining of various unpleasant symptoms. In the process of psychotherapeutic work, it turns out that the cause of the ailments is a trauma received in childhood. In such cases, the specialist helps to work through the psychological trauma and offers the patient ways to solve the problem to eliminate negative feelings and return to a full life. Here are some of them:

Psychologists note that many adults who have experienced a traumatic event show a certain amount of aggression in their behavior, which is characterized by the appearance of irrational aggressive thoughts and the performance of strange defensive actions. Effective results are achieved when a psychologist works with psychologically traumatized children. In most cases, when working with traumatized children, specialists use the following methods:

Art therapy (drawing, reading fairy tales, modeling) relieves negative thoughts, allows you to talk about your fears and look at the situation from the outside.

2. *Sand therapy* - helps the child relax, imagine himself in the place of other people and think about different options for solving the problem.

3. **Cognitive behavioral therapy** - teaches your child ways to prevent negative reactions to trauma in the future

4. **Group therapy** is suitable for children ten years of age and older. By visiting such groups, the child sees that he is not alone in experiencing terrible events, feels support, and gains confidence.

If the trauma is eliminated in time in children who have received psychological trauma, there will be no negative consequences in the development of the child in the future. Another important question is how to work with adults who were psychologically traumatized in childhood:

Often adults complain of various unpleasant symptoms and seek help from a psychologist. In the process of psychotherapeutic work, it is known that the cause of diseases is injuries received in childhood. In such cases, the specialist helps to work through the psychological trauma and offers the patient methods of solving problems to overcome negative emotions and return to a full life. Here are some of them.

The empty chair method is a method in which the patient imagines that an important person is sitting in front of him in an empty chair, with whom the traumatic event is associated. The patient is invited to express his feelings to the

"empty chair", thereby working with his trauma. After that, he himself sits in this chair and answers his questions on behalf of an important person. Thus, it is possible to revive a difficult situation, but under the supervision and support of a psychotherapist.

"**Schemotherapy**" is based on the theory that a person has beliefs (schemes) in which he automatically believes, without understanding what they are. Through dialogue, games or journals, the patient can change self-perception, overcome unnecessary fears and avoid situations that seem difficult or insurmountable, rather than "face to face with danger", can learn to face it and deal with it easily.

Eye movement desensitization and processing, a specific technique used in post-traumatic stress disorder that helps the patient to get rid of the usual reaction to emotional trauma, draws attention to internal sensations, while waving his hand (or pointer) in front of him. client's eyes. Such actions force both hemispheres of the brain to work, which helps a person not to perceive what happened as sharply as before.

In conclusion, we can say that the happy and successful future of your children largely depends on you, keep this in mind and hug your children more often for no reason. If the child is upset, put aside your work and do not be too lazy to ask him what is the reason for his bad mood, how can you help him. The direction of the future life of children and living in complete mental stability, moreover, from its comprehensive protection, depends on how their childhood passed. Only then are our children less likely to experience psychological trauma. It will be replaced by tenderness and love.

REFERENCES:

1. Егикян Манушак Араратовна (2015). Детская психологическая травма как основа формирования личности онкологического больного. Вестник университета, (5), 310-315.
2. Аптикиева Ляйля Рахматулловна (2020). Последствия психологического насилия для разных возрастных категорий. Вестник Оренбургского государственного университета, (1 (224)), 6-13.
3. Фурманов И.А., Аладьин А.А., Фурманова Н.В. Психологическая особенности детей, лишенных родительского попечительства. – Мн.: Тесей, 1999. – 160 с.
4. Холл З. Последствия сексуальных и психологических травм детства

